

**DISCUSSIONS ON TEACHING VISUAL MEANS OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF RUSSIAN GROUPS)**

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the use of means of speech expressiveness of the Uzbek language, personification, comparison in works of art. Tropes and figures are mainly used in fiction and journalism and have unequal functional activity in different spheres of communication.

The article also gives a brief description of the means of speech expression and provides examples. The work of students on the study of these means will help them consolidate their knowledge and skills in learning the Uzbek language as the state language.

Keywords: means of speech expression, personification, comparison, modern technologies, skill

One of the most important issues is improving the quality and position of the Uzbek language as the official language, strengthening the official language status, and elevating it to the level of developed languages of the world. At the same time, the emphasis should be placed on understanding the meaning of the vocabulary for reading and vocabulary in English, learning the vocabulary of the vocabulary in various communication situations, and developing the ability to use it at a well-educated level. After all, it is important to be able to convey all the opportunities and beauty of the English language, to take classes using advances in linguistics and modern technologies.

Since the early days of the National Assembly, one of the most important tasks in the educational community has been the ability to do so.

In his speech, our president, Sha'drach, Me'shach and A·bed'ne·go, emphasized: "We consider it our first priority to improve the work of all parts of the education and education system on the basis of today's requirements." ¹

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", approved on September 23, 2020, Based on the priorities set out in the PF-6097 Somli Decrees of February 8, 2019

¹ <https://www.president.uz/en/lists/view/4424>

"Confirmation of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030" and "Confirmation of the Concept for the Development of Science by 2030" in the history of the world of the theology of the theology, The issues of developing adequate skills and skills in professional activities in a divided fascial teacher and preparing competitive qualifications for regional education remain one of the most important tasks.

As our honorable President emphasized, "... Each of us should consider respect and loyalty to the official language as respect and loyalty to the motherland, and turn such a view into the rule of our lives as a focus on independence."² Each phase of a continuous education system aimed at educating young people in all aspects of our culture as perfect individuals and truly intellectual holders has been entrusted with the objectives and objectives of the educational sector.

For Russian-speaking students, knowing the Uzbek language visual aids, using them in their place, creates a foundation for students to learn and strengthen the Uzbek language as a state language. It is known that difficulties in mastering Uzbek language visual means are related not only to the ability to remember them, but also to the ability to use them later when necessary. For this purpose, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness of a certain speech idea, to change it, to search for and choose replacement means. Such operations form the ability to express the same idea using different visual means, to combine various stylistic methods, as well as to compare the selected language visual means with the tasks of expressing the idea.

The implementation of the system of exercises developed for teaching visual means of the Uzbek language to the educational process requires the appropriate preparation and planning of educational work, as well as the distribution of material related to the educational language and methodologically correct organization of the training in order to achieve greater efficiency. This means that the teacher should set specific goals and tasks in the process of preparing for each lesson, which can be clearly accomplished during the training. All types of work, methods and methods related to training should be aimed at their solution. At the same time, it is necessary to correctly organize the tasks and types of exercises, their appearance. According to many researchers, it is important to follow the sequence of giving language and communicative exercises. The main task of such exercises is to form normative speech actions on the use of figurative means of language in speech. With the help of such exercises, the training of speech actions performed with the use of visual means of the language is carried out, the skills of

²Jehovah's Witnesses — Procle. We will continue our national development path and move it to a new phase.—T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. 25-b.

performing speech activities in the Uzbek language are formed. The specific features of this type of exercises are manifested in the need to enrich the content of the language material during the speech act that can be performed. However, despite this, working on them requires relative independence from Russian-speaking students in choosing the visual means of the language, which in turn is associated with the implementation of relatively more complex perceptual actions performed by students in the process of their initial strengthening. By the end of this stage, the skills and abilities of using Uzbek language visual tools should be sufficiently strong and stable. Thus, in order to master speech skills with the help of figurative means of language, it is necessary to teach students to accept and interpret figurative means of language in accordance with the intention of the speaker, and to convey certain information with the wide use of figurative means of language. Visual means of the Uzbek language are one of the main factors of the culture of speech, which help to convey information to the listener in an interesting and impressive way in order to increase expressiveness and emotionality. They allow you to avoid repetitions and monotony, and also serve to increase the vocabulary of speakers.

Animating is one of the most common types of transference, which is the description of human characteristics in relation to inanimate and abstract objects and events. Animation is mostly found in fiction. For example, "The wind of Kokan goes crazy. It howls, roars, and squeaks on roofs, trees, and cypresses. It bends, bends, breaks trees. It cuts electric wires, makes fire. It terrorizes cabbage. It flies far and wide and sticks in lowlands, ditches, corners... A frosty day passes, a sharp night passes, but no sign of this cruel wind is visible.

It's past midnight and the wind is not letting up. He howls like a hungry wolf, and stirs snow without melting. The old woman was small among the red blankets and was lying peacefully, as if nothing had happened except for this wind... When the guests woke up in the morning, the snow had subsided and the wind had not yet subsided. After tea, they rode to Kokan... And the wind is still angry: it stirs up piles of snow, breaks tree branches, and blows and blows furiously on slate and tin roofs... (Anvar Muqimov)

Simile is a type of simile based on comparing one predeed with another for the purpose of artistic description. .

"Unsin entered his house, closed his veil, filled the sandbox with water, put tea in the teapot, and left. You see the moon. The edge of the sky is like a yellow-dirty cloud. In the midst of this dirt, low-rise houses, trees bending and swaying in the wind are black and black. The hissing wind would tempt Unsin every time he attacked and pushed him to the ground. It was easier to walk after Unsin wrapped his scarf in his hand.

In the Uzbek language, simile is formed as a speech phenomenon with the help of various lexical tools, for example, with the help of words: similar, equal, like, like, as if, like, example, bamisoli, exactly. "Then he ran like a young boy going to the bazaar with a big Eid gift from his father, he didn't pay attention to the wind blowing in front of him, and sometimes he jerked... The fire crackled and roared together, the smoke filled in the wind mixed with the darkness of the red flame, and the people who were standing far and near, he moved as if someone were lifting up the soil." (Abdullah Qahhor "Horror")

From the given examples, we can see that analogy is an important factor in increasing the impact of speech.

Formation of skills of future philologists to know the visual means of the Uzbek language is considered one of the actual issues today. It is one of the important issues to carry out scientific research on the formation of speech culture, especially among Russian-speaking students. Effectiveness as a feature of speech or text is influenced by communicative features, the goal of the speaker-writer, and the initial knowledge and imagination of the reader-listener in the process of communication. In the educational process, it is necessary to take into account the structural-semantic differences of the visual means of the Uzbek and Russian languages.

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